

Explosion venting of rich hydrogen-air mixtures in a small cylindrical vessel with two symmetrical vents

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Abstract

The safety issues related to explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures are significant and deserve more detailed investigations. Vented hydrogen-air explosion has been studied extensively in vessels with a single vent. However, little attention has been paid to the cases with more than one vent. In this paper, experiments about explosion venting of rich hydrogen-air mixtures were conducted in a small cylindrical vessel with two symmetrical vents to investigate the effect of vent area and distribution on the pressure buildup and flame behavior. Experimental results show that venting accelerates the flame front towards the vent but has nearly no effect on the opposite side. The maximum internal overpressure decreases while the maximum external flame length increases with the increase of the vent area. Two pressure peaks can be identified outside the vessel, which correspond to the external explosion and the following gas jet, respectively. Compared with the case of single vent, the use of two vents with same total vent area leads to nearly unchanged maximum internal and external overpressure but much smaller external flame length.

Keywords Hydrogen safety; Explosion venting; Vent area; Flame propagation; Overpressure

1. Introduction

Hydrogen is a promising clean energy carrier, but it is considered to be dangerous because of its extensive flammable range, low ignition energy and large burning rate. Explosion might occur once hydrogen-air mixtures are presented in confined spaces. Therefore, explosion venting is often recommended to prevent or mitigate explosion damage to the enclosures.

As is well known, one key issue of explosion venting is to select the appropriate vent area so that the explosion overpressure does not exceed a maximum permissible value. The effect of vent area on explosion venting of gas mixtures has been investigated extensively [1-11]. The experimental results of Cooper et al. [1] show that, with the decrease of vent area, the first, the third and the fourth pressure peak increases, but the second pressure peak first increases and then decrease. McCan et al. [5], Kordylewski and Wach [6] and Rocourt et al [7] found that Helmholtz oscillation occurs only in vessels with large vent areas. Special attention is paid to the effect of vent area on the peak internal overpressure [8,9], and it is found that smaller vent area leads to higher peak internal overpressure in direct vented vessel. But it is more complex in the presence of a vent duct. For example, Kordylewski and Wach [6] and Molkov et al.[10] found that an increase in duct diameter was followed by peak overpressure decrease; however, the experimental results of Ponizy and Leyer [11] revealed that an increase in vent area does not always result in a decrease in peak overpressure, which was numerically reproduced by Ferrara et al. [12] and was explained as the outcome of the competition between the burning rate and the venting rate. In other researches [13-15], critical effect of vent area on the formation of external combustible cloud and the external pressure profile was found.

In addition to the experimental investigations, numerical works about the effect of vent area on explosion venting have also been conducted to describe pressure buildup and flame propagation [12,16-20]. In the model given by Molkov et al. [21-24], the ratio of turbulence factor to discharge coefficient was introduced to account for the pressure buildup. Based on the extensive experimental and numerical works, NFPA 68 [25] and EN 14994 [26] provide the correlations for calculating vent area.

In most of the previous investigations, explosion venting in vessels with only a single vent was concerned; however little attention has been paid to the cases with more than one vent. Solberg et al. [8] found that explosions with vent openings on one wall will result in Taylor instabilities and the vent areas were suggested to be placed on as many sides of the vessel as possible. Crowhurst et al. [27] noted that the maximum overpressures of dust explosion are reduced when using several relief vent openings with the same total area and provided an empirical correlation between the external flame length and the numbers of vent, which can also be found in NFPA 68 [25]. So far, some important issues of explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixtures in vessels with more than one vent still have not been studied; for example, how does pressure build up and how does flame propagate in and outside a vented vessel in the case of two vents? And how much is the difference between the cases of single and two vents with same total vent area? In this paper, experiments on explosion venting of rich hydrogen-air mixtures in a small cylindrical vessel with two symmetrical vents were conducted to address the questions.

2. Experimental

Fig.1 is a schematic of the vented vessel in present study. Experiments were conducted in a

stainless cylindrical vessel with two symmetrical short ducts at its waist. Both the inner diameter and the length of the cylindrical vessel are 25 cm, and two quartz windows were mounted at both ends of the vessel allowing optical access necessary for the schlieren system. The length and the cross section of the ducts are 10 cm and 7 cm×7 cm, respectively. The actual vent area (A_v) was determined by the orifice plates with central square hole fitted at the exits of the short ducts. Each experiment was conducted twice, and the reproducibility of the pressure profiles, peak overpressures and flame behavior was found to be good. The experimental conditions are summarized in Table 1. In test 1 and 2, the vent area being zero means constant volume explosion; in test 3-10, one vent was used and the vent area in test 11-18 is the total of the two square holes.

Fig.1- Schematic of the vented vessel. (PT₁-PT₃: pressure transducer)

The hydrogen-air mixtures were ignited at the center of the vented vessel via steel electrodes which were 2 mm in diameter and 1.5 mm in gap width, and the ignition energy is kept about 500 mJ. Three piezoelectric pressure transducers were employed to record the pressure-time histories in and outside the vessel, which were fitted respectively in the vessel wall (PT₁), 2 cm away from one exit (PT₂) and 35 cm away from the exit outside the vessel (PT₃), as shown in Fig.1.

The experimental layout can be found in our previous study [28]. The schlieren system combined with a high-speed camera was adopted to visualize the explosion flame in the vessel. Another high-speed camera was used to record the explosion flame in and outside the

vented vessel. The frame rate of the high-speed cameras was 10,000 fps. Firstly, the vessel was sealed with blind flanges and then evacuated by a vacuum pump; secondly it was filled with hydrogen-air mixture with equivalence ratio of 2.0. Just before ignition, the blind flanges were removed quickly and a piece of paper was lightly glued to seal the vents. And then the high-speed cameras and the oscilloscope were triggered simultaneously using transistor-transistor logic (TTL) signal from a signal synchronizer to ignite the hydrogen-air mixtures and to record the flame images and the pressure-time histories, respectively. The initial pressure and temperature of the hydrogen-air mixture in all tests were 1 atm. and 280 K, respectively.

Table 1. Summary of the experimental conditions.				
Test no.	Number of vent	Vent area (cm ²)	Vessel volume(cm ³)	Duct length (cm)
1,2	0	0	12266	10
3,4	1	6.12		
5,6	1	12.25		
7,8	1	24.5		
9,10	1	49		
11,12	2	6.12×2=12.24		
13,14	2	12.25×2=24.5		
15,16	2	24.5×2=49		
17,18	2	49×2=98		

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Flame propagation in vessel

Fig.2 shows typical schlieren images of the internal flame for different vent areas. In the early stage after ignition, the flame bubble was kept spherical in all tests as shown in Fig.2. But with further expansion of the flame bubble, the flame surface was stretched to the vent, and flame distortion was found to occur earlier for larger vent area. For example, the flame has entered the duct at 5 ms after ignition in test 9 (single vent, $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$), but no obvious

flame distortion was observed till at 6 ms after ignition in test 3 (single vent, $A_v = 6.12 \text{ cm}^2$).

Fig.2- Schlieren images of internal flame for different vent areas. Test 1: constant volume explosion; Test 3 and 9: single vent, $A_v = 6.12$ and 49 cm^2 , respectively.

Fig.3 presents the flame front location and flame speed evaluated from the schlieren images by dividing the distance the flame front travels by the time difference between two frames (0.1 ms). Note that the negative sign means the direction opposite to the vent. As can be seen clearly in Fig.3, the flame is accelerated towards the vent and reaches about 9 m/s when it enters the duct in test 9 (single vent, $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$). However, venting has little effect on flame propagation in the direction opposite to the vent. Compared with test 1 (constant volume explosion), no much difference in the tracks of flame front propagating opposite to the vent can be observed in test 9 (single vent, $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$), and the flame expands with a speed oscillating from about 1.0 m/s to 2.5 m/s.

Fig.3- Location of flame front vs. time. Test 1: constant volume explosion; Test 9: single vent, $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$.

In addition, vent area also affects the formation of the cellular structures on the flame surface. As shown in Fig.2, the flame surface is still kept quite smooth except for some wrinkles at 6 ms after ignition in test 1 (constant volume explosion). However much more wrinkles appear in test 3 (single vent, $A_v = 6.12 \text{ cm}^2$) and the flame surface is not relatively smooth. When the vent area was increased to 49 cm^2 (test 9), a lot of cells appear on the bottom of the flame bubble at 5 ms after ignition, and flame cellularity evolves quickly and ends in a millisecond. The effect of vent area on the appearance of flame cellularity lies in the fact that flame elongation due to venting contributes to the appearance of the cellular structures on flame surface [5]. Larger vent area leads to higher outflow rate of gas mixtures and larger flame elongation. As a result, flame cellularity occurs earlier. When two vents with same total vent area are used, Fig.4 shows that the flame bubble is stretched symmetrically, and flame cellularity occurs earlier than the cases with one vent. As shown in Fig.4, only a few cells appear at 5 ms after ignition in test 7 (single vent, $A_v = 24.5 \text{ cm}^2$). However the flame surface has become completely cellular at that time in test 13 (two vents, total $A_v = 24.5 \text{ cm}^2$). But the difference in flame distortion and cellularity between the cases of single vent and two vents

makes no obvious difference in the internal pressure profile, as will be shown in the next section.

Fig.4- Flame images at 5 ms after ignition. Test 5 and 7: single vent, $A_v=12.25$ and 24.5 cm^2 , respectively; Test 11 and 13: two vents, total $A_v=12.24$ and 24.5 cm^2 , respectively.

3.2 Pressure profile in vessel

Fig.5 presents typical unfiltered pressure histories for different vent area. Different from the pressure profile with multi-peak for hydrocarbon-air mixtures obtained by the former researchers [3,9,20], only one dominant pressure peak can be observed due to the faster burning rate of hydrogen and the relatively small vent area in current study. The internal overpressure first increases steeply to its maximum value and then decreases gradually. Except the pressure oscillation in test 17(two vents, total $A_v= 98 \text{ cm}^2$) which will be discussed in the next section, the pressure histories vary in quite a similar way. Fig.5 also shows that the time needed for the internal pressure to decrease to ambient pressure increases with the decrease of vent area. For example, it increases from about 50 ms in test 5 (single vent, $A_v= 12.25 \text{ cm}^2$) to about 80 ms in test 3 (single vent, $A_v=6.12 \text{ cm}^2$), and a much longer time is needed in test 1 (constant volume explosion) where only the heat loss to vessel wall causes the decrease in pressure.

Fig.5- Internal pressure profiles. Test 1: constant volume explosion; Test 3, 5, 7 and 9: single vent, $A_v = 6.12, 12.25, 24.5$ and 49 cm^2 , respectively; Test 17: two vents, total $A_v = 98 \text{ cm}^2$.

Fig.6 compares the pressure-time histories in the case of single vent and two vents with same total vent area. The pressure-time histories are quite similar and no significant change of the maximum overpressure occurs when the vent area is equally divided, which is different from the result of Crowhurst et al. [27] that pressures of dust explosion were reduced when several relief vent openings with the same total area were used.

Fig.6- Comparison of internal pressure histories in the cases of single vent and two vents. Test 5, 7 and 9: single vent, $A_v = 12.25, 24.5$ and 49 cm^2 , respectively; Test 11, 13 and 15: two vents, total $A_v = 12.24, 24.5$ and 49 cm^2 , respectively.

As reported in the previous investigations about explosion venting of hydrogen [2,6], the maximum overpressure decreases with the increase of vent area. As shown in Fig.7, the

maximum overpressure decrease exponentially with the increase of vent area both in the cases of single vent and two vents with same vent area. It is worth noting that the maximum overpressure of hydrogen-air mixtures is much higher than that of hydrocarbon-air mixtures [1,3], which can be attributed to the higher burning rate of hydrogen. For example, the measured maximum overpressure is around 200 kPa when vent area is 49 cm², which yields a vent parameter $V^{2/3} / A_v$ being 10.9, where, V is vessel volume and A_v is vent area. So, compared to hydrocarbons, larger vent area is needed for hydrogen to keep the explosion overpressure below a maximum permissible value.

Fig.7- Maximum internal overpressure vs. vent area.

3.3 Flame behavior and pressure profile outside vessel

Typical images of the external flame are presented in Fig.8. When the vent area is large, for example in test 7 (single vent, $A_v = 24.5$ cm²), a fireball with a diameter much larger than the length of vent size first appears in front of the vent and then it is distorted to become a flame jet. The latter extends quickly to its maximum length, and then decreases in length and disappears at last. However, the fireball can hardly be observed when the vent area is small, for example in test 3 (single vent, $A_v = 6.12$ cm²) as shown in Fig.8. Daubech et al. [15] found that vent area has a significant influence on the formation of external cloud and a jet

like structure appears when the vent area is reduced. In current experiments, for large vent areas, the fireball is resulted from the quick combustion of the unburnt external cloud and the following flame jet forms due to the continuous combustion of the vented burnt gas mixtures which is initially hydrogen- rich. For small vent areas, for example in test 3 (single vent, $A_v = 6.12 \text{ cm}^2$), the flame jet is the result of the combustion of the “jet like structure” as observed by Daubech et al. [15].

Fig.8- Flame images outside vessel. Test 3 and 7: single vent, $A_v = 6.12$ and 24.5 cm^2 , respectively.

In this paper, attention is paid to the maximum length of the external flame, which is found to be closely related to the distribution of the vent. In the case of single vent, Fig.8 shows that the maximum length of the external flame is much longer in test 7 (single vent, $A_v = 24.5 \text{ cm}^2$) than that in test 3 (single vent, $A_v = 6.12 \text{ cm}^2$). Fig.9 presents the maximum flame length in the case of single vent (test 9) and two vents (test 15) with same total vent area. It can be clearly seen that the flame length through one of the symmetrical vents was much decreased, but the total length through the two vents has no much difference with the case of single vent.

Fig.9- Maximum flame length for single vent (top) and two vents (bottom). Test 9: single vent,

$$A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2; \text{ Test 15: two vents, total } A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2 .$$

The maximum flame lengths in tests 3-18 are summarized in Fig.10. Note that the values in the case of two vents are the flame lengths through one of the symmetrical vents. It is found that the maximum flame length increases with an increase of the vent area in case of a single vent. As discussed above, the flame jet is resulted from the continuous combustion of vent fuel-rich mixtures outside the vessel, and its maximum length should depend on the volume flow rate of vented gas mixtures. Under current experimental conditions, the vented flow is choked in most cases, so its volume flow rate increases with vent areas and as a result the maximum flame length also increases. When the vent area is equally divided, the flame length is much decreased, which follows qualitatively with the empirical equation of dust flame length ($L_f = k\sqrt[3]{V/n}$, where, L_f is flame length, k is flame length factor, V is vessel volume and n is the number of evenly distributed vents) provided by Crowhurst et al.[27] and NFPA 68 [25].

Fig.10- Maximum flame length vs. vent area.

In addition, it is found that the external pressure profile is closely related to the behavior of external flame and depends on experimental conditions. As shown in Fig.11, two pressure peaks p_1 and p_2 can be clearly identified in test 7 (single vent, $A_v = 24.5 \text{ cm}^2$), which are due to the formation of fireball and the following flame jet, respectively. When the vent area is large, a large amount of unburnt gas mixtures was discharged to form a combustible cloud in front of vent, which was ignited by the vented flame to result in an external explosion [1,14,15], and consequently the first pressure peak p_1 appears. Gas mixtures were vented at high speed following the external explosion, which leads to the appearance of the second pressure peak p_2 . But when the vent area is small, the fireball can hardly be observed in Fig.8; that is to say, no turbulent external explosion occurs, so p_1 can hardly be distinguished in test 3 (single vent, $A_v = 6.12 \text{ cm}^2$).

Fig.11- External pressure histories outside the vessel. Test 3 and 7: single vent, $A_v = 6.12$ and 24.5 cm^2 , respectively.

In the external pressure profile, which pressure peak dominates depends on the vent area and the distribution of the vents, but unfortunately no universal rule was found. When vent area is 6.12 cm^2 and 12.25 cm^2 , the second pressure peak always dominates the external pressure profile. But when the vent area is 24.5 cm^2 and 49 cm^2 , the situation may change. For example, the second pressure peak is dominant in test 9 and 10 (single vent, $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$) and the first pressure peak becomes the dominant one in test 15 and 16 (two vents, total $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$). It should be noted that vent area has no critical effect on the maximum external overpressure with the range from about 15 kPa to 50 kPa.

Critical effect of external explosion on the internal overpressure has been found in previous studies [7,9,14,29,30], which can also be found in current experiments but only in test 17 (two vents, total $A_v = 98 \text{ cm}^2$). As mentioned above, turbulent oscillation of the internal pressure occurs in this case. Fig.12 presents the pressure histories in and outside vessel. The internal pressure is effectively released due to the large vent area in test 17 (two vents, total $A_v = 98 \text{ cm}^2$). So, the pressure near vent exit (PT_2) can exceed temporarily the internal one (PT_1), which is caused by the external explosion. The turbulent oscillation of internal pressure may

be resulted from the interaction between the internal flame and turbulence generated by the backward propagating wave. It can be also attributed to the Rayleigh-Taylor instability caused by the interaction of the internal flame with the backward propagating wave and its multiple reflected waves on vessel wall. However, turbulent oscillation is absent in test 9 (single vent, $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$) due to the fact that PT_1 is larger than PT_2 when external explosion occurs.

Fig.12- Pressure histories in and outside vessel. Test 9: single vent, $A_v = 49 \text{ cm}^2$; Test 17: two vents, total $A_v = 98 \text{ cm}^2$.

4. Conclusions

The effect of vent area on flame propagation and pressure buildup during explosion venting of hydrogen-air mixture with equivalence ratio of 2 is experimentally investigated in a small cylindrical vessel with two symmetrical vents. The vent area was determined by the orifice plates with central square hole fitted at the exits of ducts. Experiments with a single vent and two vents with same total vent areas were conducted respectively. The conclusions drawn under the current experimental conditions are as follows.

Larger vent area leads to larger flame elongation to the vent and earlier appearance of flame cellularity, but the flame speed opposite to venting is independent of vent area and remains nearly constant. Only one internal pressure peak was observed in all tests, which decreases

exponentially with the increase of vent area. Oscillation of the internal pressure for large vent area occurs due to the external explosion.

Two dominant pressure peaks can be found outside the vessel. The first one is resulted from the quick combustion of the vented unburnt gas mixtures while the second one is from the vented gas jet. The increase of vent area leads to the increase of the maximum length of the external flame, and however has no significant effect on the maximum external overpressure. Compared with the case of single vent, two vents with same total vent area leads to nearly unchanged internal and external maximum overpressures but much smaller maximum external flame length.

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